

**BUILDING SELF IMPROVEMENT IN TEACHING PROCESS
THROUGH TEACHER TALK IN EFL CLASSROOM**

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Abstract: English started to get recognition from very limited number of students who was granted an access to a formal education. Unlike Dutch language, Indonesian people tend to be more open since it's not related to the colonialism language according to relationship between Indonesia and British. Even after proclamation of independence, English was declared as the first foreign language due to its necessity towards international society. With the perspective of Indonesian people in general that learning English can upgrade someone's status in the society, help to master technology and academic knowledge, and provide a better opportunity of occupation (Mappiasse & bin Sihes, 2014), English getting more attention in the learning curriculum in Indonesia. In 1989, English become a compulsory subject to be taught in the school and until today English become one of subject to be tested in national examination.

Key words: Self Improvement, Teacher Talk, Efl Classroom

INTRODUCTION

The growth of English as an international language is strongly related to the movement of globalization where the necessity of sharing a same language around the world is inevitable. Even though at first

English expanded by the military power, it is maintained and grown initially when the industrial sector in the United States of America and England become the main power in the world (Clyne & Sharifian, 2008; Crystal, 1997; Roux, 2014). Nowadays, the necessity to use English as international language expand to wider sectors such as: media, communication, education, and international travel and safety(Lauder, 2008). Furthermore, Crystal (Crystal, 1997) mentioned that approximately in 2000s, there were 1,500 million of English speakers all over the world. With the number of first speakers are 329 million, 430 million of second speaker, and 750 million others are foreign language speakers. Moreover, Kachru(1992) simplify it into three circle of English speaker, Inner circle such as: England, USA, New Zealand, Australia, Canada. Outer circle such as: India, Singapore, Malaysia, Nigeria. And the last is expanding circle such as: China, Russia, Brazil, Indonesia.

Indonesia, as a country within expanding circle, has its own history along with English. Starting from 1914 when English was started to be taught in a very limited school provided by the colonialist (Lauder, 2008). English started to get recognition from very limited number of students who was granted an access to a formal education. Unlike Dutch language, Indonesian people tend to be more open since it's not related to the colonialism language according to relationship between Indonesia and British. Even after proclamation of independence, English was declared as the first foreign language due to its necessity towards international society. With the perspective of Indonesian people in general that learning English can upgrade someone's status in the society, help to master technology and academic knowledge, and provide a better opportunity of occupation(Mappiasse & bin Sihes, 2014), English getting more attention in the learning curriculum in Indonesia. In

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According to Stern (1983) foreign language has two characters, they are: foreign language tend to be used only for travel abroad, communication with native speakers, reading a foreign literature, foreign scientific and technical works, and foreign language usually taught in formal environment since it is not used in daily activity. From the character above, it can be seen that teaching foreign language has its own challenge since the language is not used in the daily activity. Hence, teacher has a prominent role for students as input in the language learning process (Cullen, 1998). Another challenge in teaching a foreign language, which in this case is English, is that students tends to have low motivation in learning the language since it is not necessarily needed in the daily life environment and they believe that vocabulary and grammar is a separable skill to be memorized instead of set of integrated skills and subskills (Akbari, 2015).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Classroom Language and Speech Acts

Yule (1996) defines speech acts as a behaviour or activity that is done through speech. Speech or utterance produced by a speaker is intended to tell something with an assumption that the listener get the meaning of what the speaker's said. While Saputro (2015) argues that "speech acts are utterances that replace actions for particular goals in certain situations". The meaning of the utterance can be acquired through

understanding the context or the situation when the conversation happened. That is why in speech acts, interpreting an utterance cannot be separated with the context of the event, Yule (1996) names the term with speech event.

Austin (1962) classifies speech acts into two, constative and performative. Constative is an utterance that is produced in order to tell something or describe something. While performative is the utterance which is aimed to do something through speech. In order to make an utterance become performative, Austin (1962) mentions some condition that must be fulfilled. Which are:

(A.1) There must be a conventional procedure that accept and affect conventionally.

(A.2) The procedure must be uttered by the right person in the right condition.

(B.1) The procedure must be done by all involved people in order, and

(B.2) All the procedure is done.

(Gamma.1) The person involved in the procedure must have intention to do so,

(Gamma.2) The procedure must be done consequently.

From those conditions above, we can relate it to the classroom context as (1) the procedure is the learning process which in this research is teacher-students communication, (2) the right person in the right procedure is the teacher who is teaching in the classroom, (3) the procedure which is done in order and completely is the situation

happen in the classroom, and (4) the teacher must have intention in every utterance and be done consequently. It cannot be denied that in the learning activity, there must be a communication between teacher and students. The communication can be done both verbal and non-verbal.

Sadock (2006) adds that speech acts embrace performance that is not discussed in phonetics, phonology, morphology, syntax, semantic, or in other general theory of performance or acts. The special feature in speech acts is the acts that is done through speaking may not analysed grammatically, therefore, utterance's formal features are really important in interpreting the meaning of the utterance. Even in certain cases, how the listener respond to the utterance is also giving contribution in making sense of the utterance. Therefore, Austin in Sadock (2006) classified utterances into three, they are: Locutionary acts, Illocutionary acts, and Perlocutionary acts. However, due to the limitation of the research, only Illocutionary acts will be discussed further in this chapter.

1. Illocutions Acts

Austin in Sadock (2006) defines that illocutionary acts "...is the apparent purpose for using a performative sentence....", the contrast of illocutionary acts with the two others of classification in speech acts is that the utterance showing an action or making someone to do something. Therefore, illocutionary acts include as acts of ordering or requesting, asking, and stating or asserting.

In line with definition above, Searle (1999) in Basra & Thoyyibah (2017), classify five types of illocutionary acts: Assertive

Table 2.1 Type of Speech Acts

Speech act type	Direction of fit	S = Speaker; X = Situation
Declarative	Words change the world	S causes X
Assertive	Make words fit the world	S believes X

force, directive force, commissive force, expressive force, and declarative force.

Table 2.1 Type of Speech Acts

a. Declarative Force

“Declarative force has a principle that words change the world.” (Basra & Thoyyibah, 2017). Declarative force can be defined as utterance that has affect in changing a state or condition of someone.

[1] I choose Faisal to be the leader of discussion today!

The utterance [1] is addressed from a teacher to the students which change the position from ordinary students to the leader of discussion.

b. Assertive Force

Assertive force is illocutionary acts that is uttered to express a statement that related with the reality. It can also be defined as an utterance that shows speaker’s assumption about the world.

[2] If you study hard, all your hard work will be paid off

The utterance [2] expresses what the speaker believes about how learning can be useful for students' future. Even though at certain issue people might have different opinion about it, it is highly considered as assertive as long as it only expressing a statement.

c. Expressive Force

The feeling of the speaker about certain situation is the definition of this force. For example: like, dislike, happiness, sadness, and many more (Basra and Thoyyibah, 2017).

[3] I am glad to hear that you have prepared well for the national examination People can express their expression in numerous ways. This is also an exhibit that underpin a context in interpreting an utterance is a must in order to have an accurate interpretation. Therefore, in this research, the researcher records the activity in the classroom to picture the situation and the context of every speech acts produced by the teacher.

d. Directive Force

Uttering speech which is meant to ask someone to do something can be done with directive force (Basra and thoyyibah, 2017).

[4] come forward, please!

e. Commissive Force

Basra and Thoyyibah (2017) defines as "It has something to do with showing speaker's intention in the future as shown in the future."

[5] I promise to buy you ice cream after school. (Basra and Thooyibah, 2017) Utterance [5] showing someone's willingness to do something in the future. Speech acts is also needed in the classroom context since the activity of teaching and learning in the classroom must need a communication from both teacher and students, as Nurani (2015) states that speech acts in the classroom context happen in the form of sharing knowledge, conducting activities, managing classroom, and addressing instructions. Therefore, speech acts and the classroom context are inseparable learning language for classroom context is indispensable. Therefore, the more we mastering speech acts in the classroom context, the more learning objectives will be acquired by students. In order to analyse every utterances made by teacher as close as possible, theory of each classification is mentioned below:

The Implication of Teacher Talk

As Xiao-yan (2006) argues that teacher talk is really important in the language learning, which makes up to 70 percent language used in the classroom, Cullen (1998) supports the argument with a statement that teacher talk also takes part in affecting students input in learning language as in demand source of language material. Therefore, when we are discussing about the implication of teacher talk, we must also discuss about the theory of language acquisition, especially for this context, the theory of foreign language acquisition is the appropriate one since English in Indonesia is a foreign language.

Since the environment in Indonesia doesn't support the use of English as daily language, teacher become the most input of the students in acquiring English (Xiao-yan, 2006). Students are barely learn English through their environment since people use their native language and Indonesian. Hence, English teacher for foreign learner has

more role than English teacher for native learner. That is why Basra and Thooyibah (2017) urge the important of considering teacher talk in classroom context since it is the major input for students in acquiring English as foreign language in Indonesia.

Krashen (1981) introduces a “here and now” principle, where in acquiring new language, Krashen believe that the situation that is going on when someone is learning English, it helps him to comprehend the utterance addressed to him. In Indonesian context, considering that classroom provides the most effective environment for students to follow the principle without being aware with it rather than any environment such as neighborhood.

English as Foreign Language

Stern (1983) described English as foreign language as a situation where people acquire it for the purpose of going abroad, getting information from foreign literature, and communicating with the native speaker. It is also described as a language where it is taught only through formal education since the enviroment does not support the use of the language(Cullen, 1998). In Indonesia, English is determined as the first foreign language (Lauder, 2008). Unlike countries who view English as second language who make their own standard English related to their own culture, Indonesia still using native English standard whether American, British, or Australian. Hence, Indonesia is using Native standard in qualifying someone’s language ability such as TOEFL, IELTS. In the context of learning English as foreign language, there are two ways of delivering English material in the classroom, they are monolingual and bilingual. Pratiwi (2019) believe

that in monolingual approach, the more student spend time with targeted language while minimalizing the use of their mother tongue, the faster they learn the targeted language.

Hence, the teacher will only use English during the learning activity in the classroom. On the other hand, bilingual approach still uses the mother tongue in small proportion in order to enhance student's metalinguistics awareness.

Teacher Talk in EFL Classroom

Researchers and linguists agree that teacher talk has a significant role in EFL Classroom, which are learning input and classroom interaction with the student (Cullen, 1998; Krashen, 1981; Nunan, 1991; Nurpahmi, 2017). As an input, teacher become the learning source as they provide things to learn for the students and give example on how to use the target language as good as possible(Nurpahmi, 2017). Teacher talk also become a model of how English should be used, if teacher use English in a grammatically and ethnically appropriate way, students tends to imitate the way teacher use(Diffily & Sassman, 2006). In classroom interaction, teacher talk can be used in order to deliver the material for the students to learn. Hence, Teacher will produce utterance such as: lecturing, asking, responding question, explaining, and giving direction and instruction(Nurpahmi, 2017).

Conclusion

English started to get recognition from very limited number of students who was granted an access to a formal education. Unlike Dutch language, Indonesian people tend to be more open since it's not related to the colonialism language according to relationship between Indonesia and British. Even after proclamation of independence, English was

declared as the first foreign language due to its necessity towards international society. With the perspective of Indonesian people in general that learning English can upgrade someone's status in the society, help to master technology and academic knowledge, and provide a better opportunity of occupation (Mappiasse & bin Sihes, 2014), English getting more attention in the learning curriculum in Indonesia. In 1989, English become a compulsory subject to be taught in the school and until today English become one of subject to be tested in national examination.

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